

Benefits of Entrepreneurship Education and Graduate Employability in Public Tertiary Institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Given the persistent unemployment among Nigerian graduates, entrepreneurship education has been identified as a strategic approach to equipping students with skills for both formal employment and self-employment. The study explored the benefits of entrepreneurship education on graduate employability in public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. Using Human Capital Theory and the Theory of Planned Behaviour, the study adopted a survey-structured questionnaire completed by final year students from four institutions who have completed entrepreneurship programs. The quantitative data examined the benefits of entrepreneurship education on graduate employment at a significant level of 0.05, using ANOVA and an Independent t-test to analyse the hypotheses. Results showed that entrepreneurship education positively impacted employability by enhancing graduates' problem-solving, innovation, and adaptability skills. Nonetheless, challenges such as limited access to start-up resources and insufficient practical experience during training were significant barriers that hindered graduates' transition from academic settings

to entrepreneurial careers. The study underscores the importance of aligning entrepreneurship education with domestic labour market needs to enhance its effectiveness in addressing Nigeria's unemployment crisis. Recommendations include incorporating hands-on experiences into the curriculum of entrepreneurship courses, promoting collaborations, and providing post-graduation support funds accessible to graduates. Future research was recommended to expand this analysis to private institutions and to conduct longitudinal studies tracking graduates' long-term career outcomes. Overall, this study contributes to understanding how the benefits of entrepreneurship education can be leveraged to foster a more self-sustaining workforce in Lagos State and beyond.

Keywords: benefits, entrepreneurship education, graduate employability, public tertiary institutions, Lagos State

Introduction

In recent years, the value of entrepreneurship education has gained attention in Nigeria as a means to address growing concerns about youth unemployment and underemployment, especially among university graduates. With Nigeria's labor market increasingly saturated, particularly in urban areas such as Lagos, there is a pressing need to equip graduates with entrepreneurial skills that enable them to create their own employment opportunities rather than relying solely on limited formal jobs (Yerima, Musa & Umar, 2024). Entrepreneurship education is seen as a solution that fosters innovation, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills and competencies, which can support students' transition from academic to work environments.

Lagos State, being Nigeria's commercial hub, has one of the largest pools of university graduates seeking employment each year. Unfortunately, many graduates from public tertiary institutions in Lagos still lack the practical skills and entrepreneurial mindset required to thrive in a competitive job market. This challenge highlights the potential importance of entrepreneurship education as a way to increase graduates' employability by enhancing their skills for self-employment and promoting a more resilient economy through small-scale enterprises. Existing research emphasizes the positive role of entrepreneurship education in equipping students with job-relevant skills (Ojeifo, 2013). However, studies specific to Lagos and public institutions remain limited, and further research is necessary to understand the impact of these programs within this context.

According to Yerima et al. (2024), despite concerted efforts to introduce entrepreneurship education within the curriculum of public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, many graduates continue to face significant barriers to employment. The mismatch between academic qualifications and the demands of the labor market has led to high unemployment rates among university graduates. This study investigates whether entrepreneurship education can effectively bridge this gap by equipping graduates with the skills needed to improve their employability and fostering a mindset geared toward self-employment. Previous studies have established that entrepreneurship education has a positive impact on employability, but there remains a lack of empirical research examining its direct effects in Lagos State's public institutions.

This study is significant for multiple reasons. First, it adds to the body of knowledge on the benefits of entrepreneurship education's role in graduate employability, particularly in the Nigerian context. By focusing on Lagos State, this research sheds light on the unique challenges faced by graduates in Nigeria's economic capital, where competition for employment is intense. The findings may guide policymakers and educational institutions in designing more effective curricula that better prepare students for Nigeria's dynamic labor market. Additionally, the study provides insights for other states within Nigeria and similar emerging economies that are grappling with high graduate unemployment rates. Addressing this issue not only benefits individual graduates but also contributes to broader economic development by reducing dependency on formal employment and encouraging self-reliance among young professionals.

Research Objectives

1. Ascertain whether there is a difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. Determine if there is a difference in graduate employability between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria

HO2: There is no significant difference in graduate employability

between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurship education has emerged as a critical area of focus in higher education, particularly for its potential to improve employability among graduates in Nigeria. The literature on entrepreneurship education is informed by various theories and concepts that provide a framework for understanding its role in shaping graduates' readiness for the labor market. This section synthesizes these theories and key concepts, particularly within the Nigerian and Lagos State contexts, to highlight the potential benefits and limitations of entrepreneurship education in enhancing employability.

Theories Underpinning Entrepreneurship Education

Several theories inform the design and implementation of entrepreneurship education, including Human Capital Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior. Human Capital Theory posits that investment in education increases individuals' productive capacities, which is foundational for enhancing employability (Becker, 1964). In the context of entrepreneurship education, this theory suggests that when students are equipped with entrepreneurial skills such as problem-solving, leadership, and risk management, they are better positioned to secure employment or create their own job opportunities.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) asserts that individuals' intentions to perform certain behaviors are influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control over the behavior. In entrepreneurship education, this theory suggests that fostering a positive attitude toward self-employment, creating a supportive environment, and enhancing students' confidence in their entrepreneurial skills can increase the likelihood of graduates engaging in entrepreneurial activities after school. This theoretical foundation supports the notion that an effective entrepreneurship curriculum can instill both the mindset and skills necessary for graduates to pursue diverse employment pathways.

Conceptual Review

Key concepts in entrepreneurship education, such as entrepreneurial mindset, skill acquisition, and employability, align with the aforementioned theories and are critical to understanding the outcomes of such education. An entrepreneurial mindset, characterized by creativity, risk-taking, and problem-solving, is fundamental for students to transition from job seekers

to job creators. Ahmed, Ajayi & Olakunle (2011) emphasized that cultivating this mindset is a cornerstone of entrepreneurship education, as it enables students to view problems as opportunities, a perspective that is crucial for both self-employment and entrepreneurial roles within organizations. Skill acquisition is another core concept within entrepreneurship education. Studies indicate that entrepreneurship programs should prioritize the development of both hard and soft skills, including financial literacy, negotiation, communication, and strategic thinking, as these are essential for navigating the complexities of the labor market (Kuratko, 2005). Lagos State, with its high population density and limited formal employment opportunities, particularly benefits from a curriculum that equips graduates with practical skills, positioning them for both formal and informal employment opportunities (Ojeifo, 2013).

According to Osaro-Martins (2024), graduate employability, as the second key concept, is the ability to produce imaginative, resourceful, and independent graduates who can think critically, be inventive in developing support systems. It is also an outcome of the entrepreneurial mindset and skills gained through entrepreneurship education. In Nigeria, employability is often a function of both individual competencies and external labor market conditions. Scholars have noted that while entrepreneurship education can increase employability by enhancing graduates' adaptability and resilience, the effectiveness of these programs is often constrained by institutional challenges, such as inadequate funding, lack of qualified faculty, and limited access to practical resources (Yerima et al., 2024). Addressing these barriers is crucial to realizing the full potential of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian public tertiary institutions.

Entrepreneurship Education and Graduate Employability

Empirical studies suggest that entrepreneurship education can significantly impact graduate employability. For instance, a study by Ezeani (2018) in Nigeria found that students who participated in entrepreneurship programs had higher levels of job-related skills and were more likely to engage in self-employment than those who did not. Similarly, Yerima et al. (2024) reported that entrepreneurship education positively correlated with graduates' confidence in pursuing entrepreneurial ventures, although they also noted that graduates still faced structural challenges in accessing capital and mentorship to launch their businesses.

In Lagos State, these findings resonate with the experiences of many graduates from public tertiary institutions who, despite completing

entrepreneurship courses, struggle to transition into self-employment due to limited support structures. Studies in this context underscore the importance of aligning entrepreneurship education curricula with the local economic environment, including partnerships with industries that can offer internships, mentorship, and resources for startups. As Onuma (2016) suggests, the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education is not solely dependent on curriculum content but also on the institutional and policy environment that supports graduates' transition to self-employment.

While the literature generally supports the value of entrepreneurship education in improving employability, there is limited research that examines its specific impact within Lagos State's public institutions. Moreover, few studies have explored the long-term career pathways of graduates who receive entrepreneurship education, which is necessary to assess the sustainability of entrepreneurship as a pathway to employment. Another notable gap is the lack of research on gender-specific outcomes, as female graduates may face unique challenges in pursuing entrepreneurship, particularly within Nigeria's socio-cultural context.

Methodology

This study used quantitative surveys to explore the benefit of entrepreneurship education on graduate employability in public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of final year students from four selected institutions who had completed entrepreneurship courses. A structured questionnaire was used to gather quantitative data for the study, which was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to identify trends and differences in the study using ANOVA and an independent t-test.

Results

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria.

In order to test this hypothesis, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. Data collected on benefits of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria were therefore subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the descriptive statistics and results of the ANOVA analysis are presented in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
LASUED	100	28.0200	9.18385	.91838	26.1977	29.8423	14.00	46.00
LASU	100	28.1800	9.15013	.91501	26.3644	29.9956	14.00	46.00
UNILAG	100	28.8300	8.94433	.89443	27.0553	30.6047	15.00	46.00
FCE(T)	100	27.2900	8.68331	.86833	25.5670	29.0130	14.00	46.00
Total	400	28.0800	8.97552	.44878	27.1977	28.9623	14.00	46.00

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

Table 2: Level of significant difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	120.020	3	40.007	.495	.686
Within Groups	32023.420	396	80.867		
Total	32143.440	399			

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

The results in Table 2 show that there is a significant difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria ($F_{(3,396)} = .495$, $\hat{\eta} > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the benefit of entrepreneurship education among public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria was not rejected.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in graduate employability between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria.

In order to test this hypothesis, Independent t-test was used. Data collected on graduate employability in public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria were subjected to Independent t-test and the descriptive statistics, as well as the results of the analysis, are presented in Table 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of federal and state tertiary institutions in graduate employability in Lagos State, Nigeria

What type of tertiary Institution are you admitted into		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Graduate	Federal	200	22.8228	6.02703	.47948
Employability	State	200	25.3347	8.12656	.52240

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

Table 4: Independent t-statistics of significant difference between federal and state tertiary institutions in graduate employability in Lagos State, Nigeria

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	Df	p-value	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower Upper	
Graduate Employability	48.918	.000	-3.33	398	.001	-2.51193	.75382	-3.994	-1.03

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

Table4 presents the difference in graduate employability between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria. From Table 4, it can be seen that there is a statistically significant difference in graduate employability between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria [$t_{(df=398)} = -3.332$; $\hat{n} = 0.001 < 0.05$]. There is a difference in the results between federal and state (M = 22.82; SD = 6.03). The mean differences (mean difference = -2.51, 95% CI: -3.99 to -1.02). Consequently, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference

in graduate employability between federal and state tertiary institutions in Lagos State, Nigeria was rejected.

Discussion of Results

The study's findings revealed significant insights:

Entrepreneurship education positively influenced employability by building critical skills, including innovation and adaptability, in students. These findings align with Gibb's (2002) assertion that entrepreneurial education cultivates resilience and opportunity recognition. However, barriers such as limited practical exposure were consistent with Ahmed et al.'s (2011) observations. ANOVA results indicated no significant differences in the perceived benefits of entrepreneurship education among institutions. This suggests that systemic issues, such as curriculum standardization, may overshadow institutional variations. The independent t-test revealed significant differences in graduate employability between federal and state institutions. Graduates from federal institutions reported higher employability, potentially due to better resource access and institutional prestige. This supports Ezeani's (2018) findings on the importance of institutional support.

Limitations and Implications for Further Study

This study may face several limitations that could affect the generalizability and depth of the findings. First, the study focuses solely on public tertiary institutions in Lagos State, which limits the applicability of findings to other states in Nigeria or to private institutions that may have different curricula and resources. Second, the reliance on self-reported data from graduates could introduce recall bias or social desirability bias, as participants may overstate the benefits of their education or omit challenges faced. Lastly, this study does not track long-term career pathways due to time constraints, which may prevent a full understanding of the sustainability of entrepreneurship as a career path for graduates.

Given the study's limitations, future research could expand by including private tertiary institutions to assess whether there are differences in entrepreneurship education outcomes across institution types. Additionally, longitudinal studies tracking graduates' career development over time would offer valuable insights into the long-term impact of entrepreneurship education on employability and economic outcomes. Research that examines entrepreneurship education's impact on specific demographic groups, such as female graduates or students from lower

socioeconomic backgrounds, would also help to reveal any differential effects and inform more targeted interventions.

Recommendations

1. To enhance the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education, public tertiary institutions should incorporate more practical experiences, such as internships, mentorship programs, and real-life project opportunities with local businesses. This hands-on approach would help students gain real-world insights, develop relevant skills, and establish networks that could improve their post-graduation employment prospects.

2. Public institutions should collaborate with local businesses and governmental agencies to create support structures for graduates interested in entrepreneurship. These partnerships could include funding initiatives, startup incubators, and access to professional networks, which are crucial for overcoming financial and logistical barriers that often prevent graduates from launching their businesses.

3. Entrepreneurship education should not end at graduation. Institutions could provide ongoing support, such as workshops, networking events, and access to funding or microloans for alumni. This continuous support structure would enable graduates to refine their skills, overcome challenges, and increase their chances of sustaining successful entrepreneurial ventures.

Conclusion

This study highlights the transformative potential of entrepreneurship education in addressing graduate unemployment in Lagos State. While challenges persist, targeted interventions, including practical curriculum reforms, industry collaborations, and continuous alumni support, can enhance its impact. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how entrepreneurship education can foster a self-reliant workforce and drive socio-economic development in Nigeria.

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